

THE IMAGE OF WOMEN IN JANE AUSTEN'S NOVELS

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Abstract

The article studies the work of Jane Austen as a pioneer of realism in Britain. The image of women created by the writer had an enormous influence on the works of novelist's future ages of 18-19. It also deals with the profound impact Jane Austen had on the evolution of British literature, particularly her major role in ushering in the era of realism. Austen's remarkable ability to intricately weave together with tapestry of human emotions, and nuances of everyday life forms the cornerstone of her legacy.

Furthermore, the article explores how Austen's influence persists in contemporary literature and culture. Ultimately, Jane Austen's contribution in British literature remains unparalleled, leaving mark in literary landscape.

Keywords: realism, the image of women, innovation, invariably, cliché, satire, sentimental

Introduction

Jane Austen is a great British writer who, with her works, proclaimed realism in British literature. Her books are universally recognized masterpieces and captivate with their purity and "soft" British humor. Thanks to her work, J. Austin became the "First Lady" in literature and remains so to this day. The name of J. Austin has been criticized more than once, but, nevertheless, it is, as before, widely known. Nowadays, women's activities include the political, economic and cultural spheres. Western representatives of the "weaker sex" are actively seeking equal rights in society, proving that they can be self-sufficient, bright individuals with enormous creative potential. The creative heritage of the writer aroused the interest of many literary scholars, but the specifics of female characters in Austen's novels were not the subject of separate study. Jane Austen is referred to as the first lady of English literature. Because of her extensive knowledge of and accurate portrayal of English life, traditions, etiquette, and manners in the context of essentially English nature at the turn of the 18th and 19th centuries.

Jane Austen is considered a representative of the literary movement of realism, but her best novels are on the border between romanticism and realism. From romanticism in her books is the idealization of love relationships, and from realism is deep psychology and immersion in the inner world of the characters. All Jane Austen's novels are distinguished by a set of characteristic features: the simplicity of the plot, invariably crowned with a happy ending (a magnificent wedding), presented with gentle irony and what later came to be called "purely English humor" - the humor of phrases, not situations. Jane Austen was the first to use the so-called "outside perspective" in her novels - this is where humor and irony are contained. But the main thing is the young, sweet, modest girl at the center of the story who loves to read books and is afraid to give in to passions.

Throughout her life, the writer's aesthetic principles did not change: she remained a convinced realist who strived to truthfully depict the world around her. A distinctive feature of realism is the appeal of art to a direct depiction of the everyday life of people, devoid of any religious or mythological plot motivation. At the same time, Austen wrote only about what she knew

well: therefore, her novels may seem intimate, limited to the sphere of image. Austen does not cover in any way the historical events of which she was a contemporary: The Great French Revolution, the Napoleonic Wars, the Irish Rebellion and the first Luddite speeches. She deliberately limited herself to depicting the everyday life of the provincial nobility - the circle of people to which she herself belonged, whose life she knew and observed well.

Her books are recognized masterpieces and captivate with their sincerity and simplicity of plot against the backdrop of deep psychological insight into the souls of the characters and ironic, soft, truly "English" humor. Walter Scott compared Jane Austen's works to ivory miniatures. "Again, for at least the third time, I re-read Miss Austen's superbly written novel 'Pride and Prejudice'.

The place of the writer Jane Austen in the history of world literature leaves no doubt. This author is rightfully considered a classic. Of course, if it were not for this great writer in world literature, the world would not have a sense of what English literature really is.

Jane Austen was one of the first writers to boldly explore the lives of women in English society of her time. Her novels often focus on the fates of heroines, their expectations and restrictions associated with social norms and marriage. Jane Austen, as a woman in her own right, introduced alternative models for women, including the possibility of marriage for love rather than just social obligation.

The main characters of the English novelist are women, and the world depicted by Austen is shown through their perception of this world. In connection with the literary tradition of the 19th century, the reader's attention turns to the story of a girl from a quite prosperous provincial family. The author, revealing the life experience of the main character, shows the ways of forming her moral positions through overcoming life's obstacles. Its development directly reflects the educational essence that a person's spiritual growth occurs in the process of comprehending life and constant struggle aimed at overcoming the difficulties that arise for the individual.

We should pay attention to the fact that the heroine reveals the strong or weak sides of her character. The

realism of the narrative in Jane Austen's works sometimes remains in the description of sensitive scenes and the state of the characters, characteristic elements of English "sensitive" novels. Most of the artistic epics - "Pride and Prejudice", "Common Sense and Sensibility", "Northanger Abbey", "Emma" - show the reader the complex psychological world of the heroine from the first main event to the final scene with the happy main character and her chosen one. "Mansfield Park" is the only work in which the author models the heroine's life path from childhood to marriage, and "Persuasion" describes events more than eight years ago, committed by the heroine under the influence of others. We are talking about a mistake, which, fortunately for her, turns out to be correctable as the action progresses.

In Jane Austen's novels, women are depicted with complexity and depth, reflecting the expectations of the late 18th and early 19th centuries. Austen's female characters often navigate the limitations imposed by their social status, economic dependence, and the rigid gender roles of the time. Austen's female characters possess a strong sense of morality. Characters like Elizabeth from "Pride and Prejudice" or Emma from the novel "Emma" defy societal norms in pursuit of their own happiness.

Moreover, Austen's female characters come from various social backgrounds, allowing her to explore the diversity of women's experiences in that period. From the Dashwood sisters in "Sense and Sensibility", representing different reactions to social pressures, to Fanny Price in "Mansfield Park", who faces challenges as a poor relation within her wealthy family, Austen provides a portrayal of women's roles in society. Austen's novels not only critique the limitations placed upon women but also display their intelligence, and capacity for growth. Through her characters, she addresses the importance of individual agency, the struggle of autonomy, and the complexities of relationships in a society where marriage was often a woman's primary means of securing her future.

Most of the works are devoted to the theme of love and marriage. It should be added to what has been said that Austen did not at all consider marriage to be the most cherished dream of every girl. The author considered "Pride and Prejudice" "her favorite brainchild". Even the title "First Impressions" (1796-1797) reflects sentimental notes. The final choice of the title of Austen's novel was made based on the remark of Dr. Lister (F. Burney "Cecilia" (1782)), which contained the keywords "the result of Pride and Prejudice". Having shown the conflict of the beginning, the pride and prejudice of the characters, the author could not refuse to depict the deceptiveness of first impressions. The dominant theme of this text was the protagonist's deliverance from errors dictated by primary perception, their correction and the active work of the mind.

In Austen's works, heroines often find themselves in socio-economic constraints, dependent on their fathers or husbands. They are forced to adapt to generally accepted norms and restrictions, putting their own feelings and desires in the background. However, many of

Austen's heroines display strength of will and the ability to think for themselves, which makes them interesting and complex characters.

The author's themes smoothly flow from one work to another, without leaving, however, a feeling of secondary nature, and without turning into a cliché with different names. It is worth considering some of the features of Jane Austen's creative direction, using some of her most famous works.

"Pride and Prejudice" is considered one of Jane Austen's most famous works and exemplifies her feminine perspective on marriage and society. The main character, Elizabeth Bennet, refuses a marriage proposal from a profitable candidate, preferring her own feelings and respect. This demonstrates Austen's bold approach to the theme of female independence and choice.

Pride and Prejudice remains relevant more than two centuries after its original release. This happened for several reasons:

Universal Themes: Jane Austen's novel deals with universal themes such as love, society, family relationships and choosing a path in life. These topics are always relevant and understandable to readers of any time.

Strong Female Heroes: Jane Austen's heroines, including Elizabeth Bennet, embody the independence, intelligence, and courage of women. Their images will always inspire and motivate readers, especially women.

Satire and humor: The novel is full of witty satire and bright humor, which will always attract readers with its lightness and wit.

The images of the main characters reflect the author's ideal of personality: Jane Austen did not accept either a complete rejection of the principles of rationality, blind following of passions, or naked rationalism. Feeling and reason, according to the writer, must be balanced, must be in harmony. Heroes who deviate from this rule violate the norm of rationality and find themselves in difficult situations; they cannot understand other people and the motives of their actions.

Issues of marriage, not only the structure of life itself, but the responsibility in choosing a partner and companion that parents and young people themselves bear, is one of the main themes in "Pride and Prejudice."

The writer continued the traditions of G. Fielding and created "mixed characters", devoid of monolinearity. Her heroes are multifaceted, they are often deluded and make mistakes, but they are able to soberly assess themselves and overcome weaknesses and delusions. Under the influence of circumstances, the environment, and chance, their characters develop and their personality develops.

Real, widespread recognition came to Jane Austen only in the 20th century. Her psychological art, permeated with graceful irony, turned out to be in tune with the ideas of writers of the turn of the century and the first decades of the 20th century: G.-K. Chesterton, R. Aldington, S. Maugham, W. Woolf, E. Bowen, J.B. Priestley, E.-M. Forster. "Of all the great writers, Jane Austen is the most difficult to convict of greatness; she

has a special completeness and perfection,” said Virginia Woolf.

Conclusion

The work of J. Austen in British literature, although it includes romantic tendencies, is expressively outlined by the marker of realism. Her works had a huge influence on subsequent English novelists of the 18th and 19th centuries. It was with the help of Jane Austen's writing talent that the image of an intelligent, independent woman with a strong character confidently entered literature. The new heroine took the main position along with novels where exclusively the qualities of a man predominated. Austen's influence is great, and her works are still very popular today.

Jane Austen is not just a great writer, but also a philosopher, explorer of the female soul and a master of words. Her work leaves a mark on the hearts of readers, and her feminine perspective on literature continues to inspire and reflect on important aspects of life

and society. In her work, women find inspiration and support in finding their place in the world.

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